

THE IMPROVEMENT OF CONCEPTS OF THE CATEGORY OF TIME

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Annotation. This article gives an outline of the advancement of ideas of time in phonetics from the finish of the XIX century to the current day, during which the job of the emotional considers their development is uncovered. The article endeavors to respond to the inquiries, of what time is reflected in semantic time, and which job is played by the emotional (human) and calculate the formation of phonetic models of the time.

Keywords: category of time; linguistic conceptions of time; grammatical category of time; category of temporality; linguistic time: subjective factor.

Introduction. Linguistic time, like philosophical time, is very diverse. Knowing the surroundings and his inner world, a person masters all new aspects of being and, at the same time, all new aspects of time, because. “time is a general frame in which being takes place and any being can pass into time and time can move into different forms of being. The results of human cognition are accumulated in language, gradually forming a peculiar picture of the world, woven from various ideas that have ever existed and still exist. In the linguistic picture of the world, time occupies a certain noetic field, otherwise called the semantic space of time. This field is characterized by the variety of its components, both external and internal - by the variety of means of expressing temporality and the variety of times expressed with their help.

As N.K. Ryabtseva notes, “the concept of time is heterogeneous. It contains representations belonging to different worlds - physical, spiritual, mundane, scientific, verbal, actional”. The study of the concept of time (the concept in this work means a multidimensional culturally significant mental formation), and its role in the formation of the linguistic picture of the world began relatively recently - in the 90s of the XX century. Until then, linguistic studies of time focused mainly on the tense of the verb. The purpose of this work is to trace the development of ideas about time in linguistics from the end of the century before last to the present day and to identify the role of the subjective factor in their formation. In different periods of the development of linguistic science, the category of verb tense was interpreted either as a subjective category of consciousness or as the embodiment of physical and philosophical times.^[1]

¹ Vinogradov V.V. Russkii yazyk (Grammaticheskoe uchenie o slove): Ucheb. posobie dlya vuzov / Otv. red. G.A. Zolotova 3-e izd., ispr. M.: Vyssh. shk., 1986. 640 s.

The first is characteristic of the Russian linguistic tradition of the 19th - early 20th centuries. In most grammatical teachings created during this period, the tense of the Russian verb appears as a kind of subjective-psychological entity. So, according to A.M. Peshkovsky, “the speaker, using the category of time, determines the ratio of the time of action to the time of his speech. According to Peshkovsky, the time of speech is a moment of speech consciousness, i.e. the time represented by the speaker is subjective. The category of time is accordingly interpreted as a reflection of the subjective idea of the relationship between the moment of speech and the moment of a conceivable action. The result of the subjective-psychological interpretation of the category of verb tense was an "abstract scheme of three tenses" - present, past, and future. This scheme, according to V.V. Vinogradova, could not fully reflect the specifics of the tenses of the Russian verb, because it did not take into account living verb forms in all the variety of their functions and meanings. The latter began to be actively studied only in the 60-the 70s of the 20th century, which led to the expansion of the system of grammatical tenses and the creation of new grammatical theories.

A distinctive feature of the linguistic concepts of the time of the second half of the XXth century is that they persistently emphasize the objective nature of verb tenses: “The linguistic aspect of the category of time, or linguistic time (= temporality), we call the whole set of ways of expressing the essence of the physical and philosophical aspects of the considered categories”. The desire to objectify the language as much as possible, and especially the grammatical system of the language, leads some researchers to the idea that the generally accepted interpretation of verb tense as a grammatical category that determines the time of events about the moment of speech contradicts the idea of time as an objective phenomenon. In particular, N.S. Pospelov expresses the opinion that such interpretations of the grammatical category of time are based on the idealistic understanding of this category because they appeal not to the generalized meaning of the utterance, but to its specific psychological content.

According to his teaching, the grammatical verb tense is a mirror image of real tense relations and as such “directly incorporates the verbal action into reality”. However, even in the case when it is recognized that linguistic time is not a direct reflection of philosophical time, the objective nature of grammatical time is not questioned. So, in AI Smirnitsky we read: “It is clear that this or that method of counting and designating the time and the philosophical understanding of the very essence of time are two fundamentally different things. The fact that the time of this or that event or process is grammatically denoted in the language (using verb tense forms) about the moment of this speech does not in any way predetermine the philosophical concept of

time as such and does not in the least prevent what is designated in this way time was materialistically understood as real, objectively existing time independently of our consciousness. A similar point of view is expressed by linguists, recognizing the dependence of time in the language on the perception of objective time by the speaker. "The moment of speech," writes G.M. Mileikovskaya, "is subjective only insofar as it is unthinkable outside of individual acts of communication; in all other respects, the moment of speech is objective, and its establishment in the language takes place on objective grounds.

The "abstract scheme of the three times" is also objectified. According to B.L. Whorf, it is only part of a broader scheme of objectifying the world using language. He claims that the three-tense system of the verb is the result objectified idea of time as a series or points on a line - present, past, and future. (Compare with O. Jespersen: "Without a doubt, we are forced (based on the very essence of time or, in any case, by the necessity of our thinking) to imagine the matter in such a way that time has only one dimension and, thus, can be represented in the form of a straight line.") At the same time, this representation is not a reflection of philosophical time. Rather, on the contrary, one or another philosophical understanding of time arises under the influence of linguistic time. The study of "live" verbal forms leads researchers to two important conclusions: 1) about the close relationship between the category of time and the categories of aspect and mood; 2) about the interaction of various means of expressing temporal relations in language and speech.

The importance of the first conclusion lies in the fact that the discovery of a connection between tense and aspect, on the one hand, and tense and mood, on the other, made it possible to explain the ability of tense verb forms to convey various aspectual and modal shades of meanings. As you know, it is this feature of the verbal forms of time - the ability to combine the meanings of different categories - that often prompted scientists to exclude these forms from the category of time and attribute them either to the category of mood or to the category of aspect. So, for example, the analytical forms of the English verb, denoting actions in the process of their implementation in the present, past, and future, are defined by most researchers as purely aspectual (long form, demonstrating, progressive, continued form, type of development), and the construction shall / will + the infinitive used to denote future actions is often interpreted as a means of expressing modal meanings.¹²

¹² Desherieva T.I. Lingvisticheski aspekt kategorii vremeni v ego otnoshenii k fizicheskomu i filosofskom aspektam // Voprosy yazykoznaniya. 1975. № 2. S. 111-117.

Conclusion. Finally, the subjective factor can be found in the connection of grammatical tense with the categories of mood and aspect. A.V. Bondarenko believes that this connection, as well as the difficulties arising from it in interpreting the same forms of the verb, indicate the presence of modal-temporal and aspectual-temporal connections in this language. Modality, as is known, manifests itself primarily as an expression of a person's attitude to the stated fact. Due to aspectuality, the situation is distributed in time: it can be compressed, stretched, repeated, etc. Interacting with the indicated categories in language and speech, temporality acquires a human character, because conveys not temporal relations as such, but how these relations are organized in the minds of people: "For us, the sense of time and our internal attitude to it are much more important than the awareness of time as physical Newtonian duration, the fullness of time with events and the quality of time is more important than its natural course. For a person, time does not flow evenly and measuredly - it slows down its run or stops altogether when you wait, it always speeds up when you are in a hurry somewhere. We have to accept time as it is given to each of us - with its shortages, lengths, with its relativity, and unreliability. The above allows us to draw the following conclusion: the presence of close modal-temporal and aspectual-temporal connections in the language is because the models of time that exist in the minds of its speakers are of a pronounced subjective psychological nature. The latter, in turn, is explained by the fact that "man, as a thinking and feeling being, determines the time to himself."

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